

Simultaneous HPLC determination of vitamin C and carboxylic acids

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A simple reversed phase HPLC method using 20 mM phosphoric acid in water as mobile phase is reported for the separation of ascorbic acid (vitamin C) and other carboxylic acids, viz. oxalic acid, tartaric acid, malic acid, citric acid and propionic acid. The separation of different carboxylic acids on reversed phase column using ion suppression technique are discussed. The method developed may be used for the analysis of fruit juices where these acids are important constituents. A typical example of sweet lime juice is given to demonstrate the applicability of the method for sample analysis.

Ascorbic acid (vitamin C) and other carboxylic acids, viz. citric acid, malic acid, oxalic acid, propionic acid and tartaric acid, studied in the present work are among the important constituents of plant materials. The maturity, ripeness and spoilage of plant foods as well as most of the fermented processes can be characterized by studying the acid content and composition. Some of these acids are also used as preservatives in the food and beverages. In pharmaceutical industry these acids are used as antioxidants, acidulants, preservatives and drug absorption modifiers¹. Several methods are reported in the literature for the determination of these acids in fruits, plant materials, food products, beverages and pharmaceutical products based on various analytical techniques, such as titrimetry, spectrophotometry and chromatography depending on the matrix and the desired analytical sensitivity². High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) by virtue of its selectivity, reproducibility and sensitivity is now extensively used in the study of these acids covering all aspects. HPLC analysis of carboxylic acids covering the applications for analysis of fruits, spices, plant materials and food material have been reviewed³. It is carried out using different modes and principles such as normal phase, reversed phase, ion pair, ion exchange, ion exclusion etc. coupled with UV, RI, diode array and conductivity detectors⁴. Ion-suppression is probably the relatively simple technique to be adopted for the analysis of carboxylic acids⁵ as it can be practiced with standard reversed phase column, use of buffers and a UV detector. Various mobile phases have been used to achieve resolution between ascorbic acid and other carboxylic acids on the reversed phase columns depending on the nature and type of the sample. In the case of fruit juice, for example, phosphate buffers, buffers with organic modifiers, aqueous ac-

ids etc. have been used. The addition of acids to mobile phase decreases the pH and suppresses the ionization of the acidic groups of the analytes³, therefore proper concentration of the acid in the mobile phase is critical for achieving good resolution.

Results and discussion

In the present work, aqueous phosphoric acid (20 mM) pH 2.0 was used as mobile phase. This mobile phase gives good resolution between the carboxylic acids present in the citrus fruit juice and vitamin C. The order of elution of different carboxylic acids is determined by their pK_a values⁶. The pH of the mobile phase is known to have fundamental effect on the retention of ionic analytes as it is the neutral form, which is more hydrophobic and hence retained longer on the reversed phase column. This explains the longer retention of propionic acid (pK_a 4.37), (t_R 7.73 min), citric acid (pK_a 3.08), (t_R 4.87 min) and malic acid (pK_a 3.40), (t_R 4.34 min) as the mobile phase pH 2.0 is well below the pK_a values and they remain in the protonized form. Similarly the proximity of the pK_a values of oxalic acid (pK_a 1.23), (t_R 1.74 min) and tartaric acid (pK_a 2.98), (t_R 2.04 min) to the mobile phase pH values explains their shorter retention as they are in partially or fully ionized form. Ascorbic acid (pK_a 4.10), (t_R 2.90 min) elution however cannot be explained on the basis of ionization, as it is a 3-keto-l-gulonolactone and not a carboxylic acid. Its retention seems to follow the normal separation pattern on the reverse phase columns based on the differential retention of analytes according to their hydrophobicity.

Thus it is seen that the mobile phase containing aqueous phosphoric acid (20 mM) gives good resolution among carboxylic, dicarboxylic and hydroxy carboxylic acids along

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with vitamin C, which are found together in the citrus fruit juices. The low pH (2.0) has an added advantage in that it protonates the column silanols and reduces their chromatographic activity⁷ which is preferred for reversed phase chromatographic analysis. Also a low pH method is generally more rugged because small changes in pH are less likely to affect the retention of the analytes.

Fig. 1. Standard chromatogram for mixture of acids : (1) oxalic acid, (2) tartaric acid, (3) ascorbic acid, (4) malic acid, (5) citric acid, (6) propionic acid at 0.1, 1.0, 0.1, 0.01, 1.0 and 1.0 mg/ml, respectively.

The linearity studies were carried out for ascorbic acid and citric acid, as they are the major components of the citrus fruit juice. Ascorbic and citric acid solutions in the range of 10–50 ppm and 200–1000 ppm, respectively, were injected in triplicate and average area counts were plotted against concentrations. Both acids show very good linearity with a correlation coefficient of 0.9998 for ascorbic acid and 0.9997 for citric acid. The precision of the method was studied by injecting ($n = 5$) a single sample solution of ascorbic acid (10 ppm) and citric acid (200 ppm) and finding out the coefficient of variation. The C.V. for ascorbic acid and citric acid was 3.6 and 2.0%, respectively. The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantitation (LOQ) were calculated by analyzing 10 ppm solution of ascorbic acid and 200 ppm solution of citric acid by the proposed method. The LOD ($LOD = 2 \times N \times LD \text{ conc/S}$) and LOQ ($LOQ = 5 \times LOD$) for ascorbic acid was found to be 0.013 ppm and 0.065 ppm while for citric acid it was 0.13 ppm and 0.65 ppm, respectively. The applicability of the proposed method of analysis for citrus fruit juices was studied by procuring three sweet lime samples from the local market and esti-

Fig. 2. Chromatogram for sweet lime juice. Peaks identification as in Fig. 1.

imating the concentration of ascorbic and citric acid in them. The results are presented in Table 1. A typical chromato-

Table 1. Ascorbic acid and citric acid content of sweet lime samples (mg/100 g of juice)

Sample No.	1	2	3
Ascorbic acid	25.00	17.87	19.52
Citric acid	723.60	568.09	741.70

gram of sweet lime juice (Fig. 2) showing the distinct presence of ascorbic acid, citric acid and other carboxylic acids demonstrates the utility of the present method for the analysis of fruit juices. The juice samples prepared by the proposed method were extracted from fresh fruits and were analyzed immediately to avoid changes in vitamin C content by light, temperature, humidity, storage etc.⁴. The above discussion shows that the proposed method is suitable for the analysis of carboxylic acids and vitamin C in fruit juices.

Experimental

Equipment and conditions :

Knauer HPLC, isocratic system, comprising of a Ministar-K 500 pump, a 20 μ l injection loop and a K-2500 UV-Vis variable wavelength detector. Separations were

carried out on Knauer reverse phase column Eurospher 100, 5 μm C18, 250 \times 4 mm ID. Peaks were processed with CHEMITO C 5000 integrator. The mobile phase 20 mM *ortho*-phosphoric acid was used at a flow rate of 1 ml min^{-1} .

Standards :

Ascorbic acid, citric acid, malic acid, oxalic acid, propionic acid, tartaric acid and *ortho*-phosphoric acid were of AnalaR reagent grade. HPLC grade water was used for analysis. Stock solution of 1 mg ml^{-1} of each acid was made in the mobile phase. These acid solutions were appropriately diluted for the analysis. Standard chromatogram of the mixture of acids is shown in Fig. 1.

Sample preparation :

Fresh lemons and sweet limes were procured from the market for extraction of juice. The juice was extracted from the fruits using clean domestic glass crusher. A portion of 5 g of juice was first filtered through Whatman filter paper no. 42 and then through 0.45 μm filter under suction. Finally the volume was made up to 50 ml with mobile phase.

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